

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF DRAMA ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the pedagogical significance, goals, and objectives of dramatization activities in preschool educational institutions from a scientific and theoretical perspective. The study highlights the importance of play activities in the development of preschool children and emphasizes dramatization as one of the most effective forms of such activities. It explains how dramatization contributes to the development of children's creative thinking, speech culture, imagination, and emotional growth.

The preschool education system is one of the important components of the continuous education system and plays a special role in the all-round development of children. It is precisely during the preschool years that a child's personality is formed, laying a solid foundation for their cognitive, emotional, social and creative development. During this period, important skills such as understanding the environment, social relationships, and expressing one's own thoughts freely are developed.

The main form of activity for preschool children is play. During play, a child perceives the world in their own unique way, imagines various situations, and reveals their creative potential. For this reason, the widespread use of play-based technologies in educational activities is of significant pedagogical importance. One such type of activity is dramatisation. Dramatisation is used as an effective pedagogical tool to develop children's creative activity, form their speech culture, and provide aesthetic education. During the dramatisation process, children bring events to life on stage by performing various characters, express their feelings and develop their artistic imagination.

Drama activities increase children's verbal activity, develop their imagination and fantasy, and also foster teamwork skills. Therefore, the effective organisation of dramatic play activities in pre-school education institutions is considered one of the key pedagogical tasks.

From this perspective, scientifically studying the aims and objectives of dramatic play activities in preschool education institutions and applying them effectively in the pedagogical process is one of the pressing issues.

The theoretical foundations of dramatic play. In pedagogy and psychology, dramatic play is regarded as an important type of activity that contributes to children's creative

development. In the process of dramatisation, children create various characters and express events in an artistic form through dramatic games, role-play and stage scenes.

According to psychologists, dramatic play has a significant impact on the emotional and social development of preschool children. This is because during the process of staging, a child not only expresses their own thoughts and feelings but also strives to understand the emotions of others. This helps to develop empathy, that is, the ability to recognise the feelings of others.

The activity of dramatisation is based on a number of pedagogical principles:
taking into account the children's age and individual characteristics;
ensuring creative freedom;
applying a pedagogical approach based on play;
creating an atmosphere of teamwork and cooperation;
using elements of aesthetic education.

In early years settings, dramatisation is often based on fairy tales, stories, poems, and children's literature. This helps to develop children's artistic thinking, language skills, and their interest in books.

The aim of drama activities: The main aim of drama activities in pre-school education is to ensure the all-round development of children, developing their creative and aesthetic potential.

Through drama activities, the following educational objectives can be achieved:

Firstly, to develop children's creative abilities. During the drama process, children create various characters, imagine scenarios, and express their imagination.

Secondly, ensuring speech development. Expressive delivery of dialogues, monologues and poems during the performance process expands children's vocabulary and enhances their fluency.

Thirdly, the formation of aesthetic education. As staging incorporates elements of theatre, music, visual arts and literature, it develops children's ability to appreciate beauty.

Fourthly, developing social skills. Drama is a group activity that fosters cooperation, mutual respect, and a culture of teamwork in children.

Fifthly, supporting emotional development. During the performance process, children express a variety of emotions and learn to manage them.

Aims of Dramatic Play: In early years settings, dramatic play fulfils the following educational objectives.

The educational task - drama serves to develop moral qualities in children. Through dramatic scenes based on fairy tales and stories, children come to understand concepts such as good and evil, friendship, compassion, justice, and honesty.

Educational task – the process of staging broadens children's knowledge. Through stage scenes they acquire new information about natural phenomena, the animal kingdom, human relationships and various professions.

Developmental function – staging broadens children's creative thinking, imagination and fantasy. It also strengthens their speech, memory and attention.

Social function - staging is a collective activity that develops social skills in children, such as communication, cooperation and mutual assistance.

The aesthetic function - staging is an activity that unites various art forms. This process helps to develop children's aesthetic taste and increase their interest in art.

Types of dramatisation in preschool education:

Role-play games are one of children's favourite activities, in which they take on the roles of various professionals, fairy-tale characters or animals.

Fairy-tale dramatisation — children create stage scenes based on fairy tales. This broadens their imagination and enhances their speech activity.

Puppet theatre — is considered one of the most effective forms of dramatisation for young children. Using puppets, children bring the events of the fairy tale to life.

Musical dramatisation involves expressing dramatic events using elements of music, song and dance.

Improvisational drama involves children creating scenes independently, based on their own imagination.

In conclusion, drama in early years settings is a vital pedagogical tool for the holistic development of children. Through this activity, children's creative abilities, speech culture, emotional stability, and social skills are developed.

Furthermore, staging performances cultivates children's aesthetic taste, enhances their interest in art, and provides an opportunity for them to express their creative potential. Therefore, the effective organisation of staging activities in pre-school education institutions is considered one of the key responsibilities of educators.

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